

TOWARDS A SMART NETWORK SCHEMA BUILDER USING ANONYMOUS AND IMPLICIT INTERACTION DATA

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Abstract

Due to an ever-increasing prevalence of intelligent systems and intelligent features, the need for smart user guidance in systems is slowly transforming into an expectation. Such techniques have already been thoroughly explored for cases such as smart action and visualization recommendations. They are usually facilitated through the use of recommender systems trained on either explicit user content or implicit user interaction data. Since using explicit user data may cause potential privacy issues and data leakage, using implicit data is the safer option for any end user. A domain where such approaches would be of great benefit but have yet to be extensively explored is the area of interactive network modelling and exploration. Therefore, as part of this work, we introduced a first prototype in an existing visual analytics and network modeling tool called Collaboration Spotting X. We extend the tool's interactive network schema builder used for iteratively modeling search results as networks with a prototype of a recommender system based on implicit interaction data sequences. The newly introduced recommender system prototype aims to aid users in their network modelling journey by either recommending possible new network schemas or incremental network schema modifications using only synthetically generated interaction data. Due to the importance of user aspects in adaptive user interfaces as part of this work, a prototype user interface implementation is also introduced and evaluated through user interviews.

INTRODUCTION

User interfaces (UI) that adjust based on users' interactions with a system have been explored extensively in the past [1]. Applications with such UIs usually have a particular user model that changes over time with new interactions and provides UI change suggestions to users or adjusts the UI automatically [1]. This task is usually handled by recommender systems that provide recommendations based on user action patterns or user content [1, 2]. However, using explicit user content may have potentially devastating privacy issues [3]. Even more so in the process of data modelling or data analysis where accidentally exposed analysis aims or findings may cause harm to companies or institutions as well as individuals. Therefore, as part of this work, we only focus on implicit user and interaction data.

To explore how such recommender systems could be used to support users in their data analysis journeys in a novel context, multiple recommender system models are built in Collaboration Spotting X. This system provides users with an

environment for visual information retrieval, network-based analysis and data modelling, particularly network modelling [4]. One of the core aspects of the system is visualizing search results as networks whose topology can be changed through an interactive network schema builder. Past evaluations in the form of interviews have indicated that many users need clarification and help with using the interactive network schema designer to analyze their data.

To support users in a privacy-conscious way, as part of this work, we explore multiple approaches to providing completely new schema suggestions and potential iterative changes in existing network schemas using interaction data and implicit data features. Since automatic changes may unpleasantly surprise users, the system suggests these changes to users as part of an extended schema builder UI [1]. We explore various features extracted from anonymous interaction data for building multiple recommender systems to identify the best-performing ones. Finally, we evaluate the resulting systems using standard evaluation measures and user interviews.

Based on the above-described potential for recommender systems in visual interactive network analysis, as part of this work, we introduce a recommender system prototype to an interactive network schema. As part of this work, we aim to answer the following research questions:

1. **How can a sequential recommender system aid users in exploring interactive network schemas?**
2. **How can interactive network-based visual analytics tools improve users' exploratory interactions through recommender systems?**

BACKGROUND AND RELATED WORK

VISUAL ANALYTICS AND NETWORK MODELING

Visual analytics systems usually rely on a combination of information visualisation and automated analysis approaches combined with a human in the loop with the main aim of supporting the analytical workflow, creating a model that accurately describes a part of reality that the user needs to answer their analysis questions and the creation of insights that answer the research questions of the system user [5–7]. One of the main psychological models used to describe the visual analytics workflow is sensemaking [8, 9]. The sensemaking process includes multiple activities performed non-linearly and can be defined with two main loops: the foraging loop and the sensemaking loop. The former focuses on retrieving, filtering and extracting information into a

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particular representation appropriate for analysis, while the latter focuses on extracting hypotheses and externalising knowledge [8].

To represent data in an appropriate representation or schema that supports users' question-answering and insight generation, experts traditionally used programming approaches to pre-process data before being able to use it in a tool. For the case of network analysis and network modelling, this is still true, with only a few tools exploring the possibility of providing users with an approach to modelling networks by users with no need for coding. Examples of such tools include Ploceus and Origraph, which depict a visual network schema and enable users to model data into a network representation based on it [10, 11]. Another example of such a tool is Collaboration Spotting X, which provides users with a network schema and a history of network representations over time [4]. However, for larger datasets with many features, these schema representations are complex and confusing for users. They would benefit from additional automatic guidance, which would help users create and modify schemas.

ADAPTIVE USER INTERFACES

An approach that could help support users in their network modelling process is adaptive user interfaces (AUI). AUI adapt their functionality or actions based on the user's needs and interactions with the system [1, 12]. However, before introducing an AUI into a system, multiple aspects, such as the difficulty and routine of tasks that are performed in a system, the users that will be using the system, and the level to which a system is adaptive [12]. For example, AUIs that provide some level of adaptivity but let the user efficiently perform tasks manually are more beneficial than fully automated AUIs in cases where a user has to perform non-routine tasks [12]. Recent advancements in machine learning techniques can be used to facilitate such interfaces [13]. Techniques such as deep learning, particularly in the context of action recommendations, could enhance users' experiences in complex visual analytics systems and provide users with the necessary support in their analysis workflows.

RECOMMENDER SYSTEMS

Sequential recommender systems (SRS) are recommender systems (RS) dealing with sequences of user-item interactions and aiming to suggest new possible items to interact with or interactions [14, 15]. These items could include items to buy or user interface (UI) elements to interact with or use. Therefore, such systems may be used for adaptive user-interfaces.

An early example of using recommender systems to recommend the next webpage visit is through the use of pattern mining [16]. This system analyzes the user browsing history, identifies common patterns and provides recommendations for the next possible pages based on the n previous visited pages. Another earlier example of a sequential recommender system technique is using Markov Chains in combination with matrix factorization [17]. With the improvement in

hardware capabilities and advances in neural network architectures and modern deep learning (DL), the use of DL solutions has become more approachable and more effective in tasks such as sequential recommender systems. An example of a solution using DL, in particular deep recurrent neural networks combined with gated recurrent memory units for creating an SRS used for adaptive user interface (AUI), is described by [18]. Unlike previous approaches that used pattern mining or Markov chains, this approach considers users' long-term interaction histories. The evaluations also indicate that such models are more accurate than past models [18].

Further evolutions of such models include long short-term memory (LSTM) [19, 20] and gated recurrent unit (GRU)[21, 22]. Alternative DL architectures such as convolutional neural networks and graph neural networks have also shown great promise in the context of SRS and can be used to model complex interaction patterns and patterns between not-adjacent interactions [14]. An example of graph neural networks for an SRS is described by [15]. They introduce an architecture called SURGE, which aims to address the issue of using implicit user feedback through interactions and users' change of interest over time. Despite the evaluation of SURGE indicating its effectiveness, the authors note that further user studies have to be conducted.

MODEL AND SYSTEM DESIGN

Since CSX includes an overview and detail schema, representing a co-occurrence and a multivariate network, the recommender system model has to recommend schemas and actions for two separate network types. The CSX system is connected to the OpenAlex API [23]. Therefore, users can access the metadata of approximately 240 million papers and explore them as interactive network representations.

As part of this work, we created models specifically for the network schemas of OpenAlex. Four separate models were created, one for schema recommendations and one for action recommendations for each network type, to observe potential problems in data or in our hypotheses easily. Due to CSX being designed to respect users' privacy and users being intimidated by the network schema and having trouble understanding it, there was a lack of interaction data that could be used for a recommender system.

DATA PREPARATION

Due to the lack of interaction data, multiple synthetic data sets were prepared for the recommender system-building process. The datasets aimed to mimic simple user interactions with the schema representation. The two datasets were constructed by defining a set of potential schemas users may want to build using CSX. For the overview network representation, 67 unique schemas were prepared, and for the detail network representation, 55 schemas were prepared. Based on these schemas, 10,000 synthetic user sessions with lengths of 10 to 300 were created for the overview and detail

representation. The schemas were randomly picked for each session to simulate potential user exploration paths.

Incremental schema changes were needed to generate input datasets for the action recommendation models. Users usually perform multiple actions on the schema before applying a new schema to the system and generating a network based on it. These actions may include removing or adding edges, changing the node representation, adding node properties and changing the edge cardinality. A sequence of schemas representing incremental changes was generated for each sequential pair of schemas from the sessions mentioned above. Since the model prototype architecture supports only a fixed length input, the sessions had to be split into sequences of ten schemas. The final representation of the schema recommendation dataset included a list of sessions with ten schemas, each with an additional schema as the next schema or label. On the other hand, the action recommendation dataset was represented by a list of sessions with ten schemas and an action or label for each.

RECOMMENDER SYSTEM

The recommender system models were built using the Python PyTorch library [24]. Due to this system being a prototype, multiple simple models were built to test the concept and answer the initial research questions. Based on the insights gathered from related work, the architecture chosen for this prototype was based on LSTM. The two models used for schema recommendation had a single layer with 32 neurons and a linear output layer each and were trained for 350 epochs. Cross entropy was used for measuring the loss, and Adam was used as the optimizer with an initial learning rate of 0.001. On the other hand, the action recommendation networks had four layers with 32 neurons each and were trained for 35 epochs using the same loss function and optimizer.

Additionally multiple sizes of input data were tested for training the models. The final dataset size used for the schema recommendation models was 5000 sequences with 10 schemas each. On the other hand, the dataset size used for the overview and detail action recommendation models was 200000 and 100000 sequences with 10 schemas each. The datasets were split using a 60:20:20 ratio for the schema recommendation models where 60% of the data was used for training, 20% was used for validation, and 20% was used for testing. On the other hand, the datasets used for the action recommendation models were split using an 80:20:20 ratio.

The detailed loss values of each of the models can be seen in Tab. 1. It can be observed that the two schema models were overfitted to the sample data, which can be potentially explained by the input only being transitions between schemas. Due to the exploratory and prototype nature of this work, this was acceptable, but it was noted that it should be improved in the future.

After the training, the models were implemented in Collaboration Spotting X and introduced in the user interface as depicted in Figure 1. Once the user performs the initial search and is shown the search results as a network, they can

Table 1: Average loss values for the schema and action recommendation models. OS and DS stand for overview and detail schema recommender model, respectively. OA and DA stand for Overview and detail action recommender model, respectively. Train. L., Valid. L. and Test. L. represent the average training, validation and test loss values.

Model Type	Train. L.	Valid. L.	Test. L.
OS	0.3056	13.4627	12.9616
DS	1.1308	10.0776	9.9880
OA	0.7439	0.7357	0.7464
DA	0.9919	0.9589	0.9639

interact with the recommender system results. When a user modifies the schema using any of the action interactions, a new set of action interactions is shown to them. Once they apply the schema and create a new network out of it, the schema recommendations refresh, as well as the action recommendations refresh. This provides the user with a new set of recommendations based on their past interactions every time they interact with the system.

Figure 1: The Collaboration Spotting X dynamic network schema and the recommendations. The buttons at the top of the schema builder (1) represent schema recommendations. The smaller buttons at the bottom of the schema (2) represent action recommendations. By clicking on one of the schema or action recommendations, users automatically change the entire schema or just one schema property, respectively. Once the change has been made, they can further change the schema or apply it to their data.

USER INTERVIEWS

To answer the above-identified research questions, we interviewed four experts who were familiar with the CSX system. The experts included a data scientist, a doctoral student in computer science, a senior research fellow and a senior software engineer. After being re-introduced to CSX, they were given fifteen minutes to interact with the system and explore the new schema and recommendation features.

After the interactive session, they were asked the following questions relating to their experience:

- How would you describe the relevance of the recommendations received by the recommender system?
- For what tasks would you use the schema and action recommendation systems?
- What would you like to improve or add to the recommender system?

All experts observed that the schema recommendations are somewhat random, while the action recommendations are very relevant to the current schema. Furthermore, all noted that the seemingly random generation resulting from overfitting helped them explore the new schemas and gather inspiration for their exploratory journey. On the other hand, the action recommendations were recognised as being more useful for small incremental interactions when the schema needed finer adjustments.

They noted that while the recommendations were helpful, the recommendation buttons should be adjusted to reflect better the change they will cause. Moreover, the experts expressed the need for expanding the recommendation features to the entire analysis process by recommending actions based on the network data being viewed by the user, recommending potential alternative visualisations, and even recommending potential new search queries in the context of CSX.

Finally, during the exploratory interaction phase, it was noted that using the recommended schemas and actions is much easier than manually creating entire schemas and, therefore, more inviting to use. It was further observed that the users better understood what they could do with the interactive network schema after applying the recommended actions and seeing how they modified the schema. However, some still needed help understanding how the actual schema affects the network representation and therefore suggested that there should be a more precise explanation of what each of the schemas changes in the network representation.

Based on the following answers, the answer to research question 1 is that the recommender system can help users explore, adjust, and, in some cases, even learn how to use interactive network schemas. Due to the complexity of such a system, users need multiple forms of support, which can be provided using recommender systems. Furthermore, it was observed that further support is needed for the user to understand how the schema affects the network representation. The answer to the first question can also serve as a partial answer to the second question. However, interactive network-based visual analytics tools may improve users' exploratory interactions by adding extensive recommendation support throughout the system. For example, leveraging information about the data explored by users' systems can further expand user support through network modelling functionality and insight discovery. However, this may come at the cost of potential privacy issues if not implemented appropriately.

Additionally, it may be possible to use only user interactions in other areas of a visual analytics tool to indicate how interesting a schema is to a user and, based on this predict further schemas. Finally, systems could potentially support users by providing recommendations for system-wide actions based on the current context.

CONCLUSION

As part of this work, we introduce a prototype of a sequential recommender system for interactive network schema modelling. The system was built using synthetic data and trained using the long short-term memory neural network architecture. The system recommends users' potential next network schemas and incremental network adjustments. After training, it was integrated into the network-based visual analytics system Collaboration Spotting X. The system consists of four models for recommending schemas and actions of the overview and detail view. It was evaluated through user interviews. The results of the evaluation indicate that such an approach is well received by users and serves as a tool for exploration and idea gathering, easier interaction with complex network schemas, as well as learning support for novice users. Identified improvements to the system include the expansion of such a system to other areas of interactive network analysis, improvements to the user interface of the recommender system and the consideration of the data being explored by the user in the system. We aim to expand and enhance the system with the suggested recommendations in future work. Furthermore, we aim to explore the potential unification of the four distinct models into one, support multiple preloaded and user-uploaded dataset schema and action suggestions, and recommend schemas and actions based on user observations in the system. To improve the schema recommendation models, we will explore the introduction of additional contextual information, such as areas of the user interface the user was interacting with before switching to a new schema. Finally, we aim to explore other neural network types, such as graph neural networks and additional schema encoding strategies, such as vector embeddings, for better recommendation accuracy.

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